

BIOLOGY OF RUBIA TINCTORIUM L DISTRIBUTED IN SURKHANDARYA CONDITIONS

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Annotation. *Rubia tinctorum L is also a heat and moisture-loving plant with a long growing season, so it is also common in the Surkhandarya oasis in the south of the country. It is widely used in dyeing and medicine. That's what this article is about.*

Keywords. *Rubia tinctorum L, Asia Minor and Central Asia, Abu Ali Ibn Sino, Surkhandarya region, 19th century, red, pink, purple, orange, brown.*

The original range of *Rubia tinctorum* is the Mediterranean, Asia Minor and Central Asia, Eastern Europe. As a wild plant, it has been naturalized in the south of the European part of Russia, in the Caucasus, in some places.

It is found in trees and shrubs along rivers, on the banks of irrigation canals, on rocks, in steppe meadows, on the banks, in light pine forests, in abandoned gardens, vineyards, and on dams. *Rubia tinctorum L* is a heat and moisture loving plant with a long growth period. In dry years it develops poorly, seed yield is significantly reduced.

The plant does not adapt to the mechanical composition of the soil: it grows in sands, loams and solonchaks, but the most suitable for Mador (especially when grown in culture) are light and medium-textured fertile soils. A plant with a strong main root with elongated thick rhizomes. The roots and rhizomes are covered with a reddish-brown bark. Thin, climbing, very branched tetrahedral stems along the ribs sit with thorny spines bent backwards. Shoots begin to grow in mid-May.

The leaves are dense, stiff, light green, often bent spines along the bottom and edges, lanceolate or elliptic, up to 10 cm long, up to 3 cm wide, overgrown or short-winged petiole, located at 2 - angles. 4-6 women. The flowers are small, star-shaped, yellow, apical and axillary in semi-umbels. The corolla is funnel-shaped and has 4 (5) divergent limb pieces at the top, which is 1.5 times larger than the tube. The plant blooms from June to August.

Fruits - succulent black legumes 5-9 mm long, 1-2 seeds - ripen in August-November in the first year of vegetation. Propagated by seeds and vegetatively, in culture - by segments of seeds and rhizomes. The history of cultivation of *Rubia tinctorum L* is primarily due to its use as a bright red dye. The roots of biennial

plants are used to obtain dyes. Depending on the echant, dyes of different colors are obtained - red, pink, purple, orange and brown.

Madder extracts, sold under the Krapp name, were most popular in the 19th century, before the era of aniline dyes. It is impossible to determine exactly when they started growing creeks in Russia. It is known that in 1745 Mikhail Lomonosov, together with other professors of the Academy of Sciences (Gmelin and Sigezbek), studied samples of spices sent from Kizlyar; experiments on artificial planting of creek plants were proposed [4] [page not specified 1831 days]. In 1787, the government ordered pasta seeds from Anatolia, and in 1812, the Imperial Free Economic Society awarded a gold medal and a cash prize for better reproduction than wild Astrakhan.

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